

Sorption of some Normal Aliphatic Alcohols by Egg Albumin

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Sorption of methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl, *n*-butyl and *n*-amyl alcohols on egg albumin has been studied at 30° by using the quartz fibre spring technique. The sorption is related inversely to the molar volume of the sorbate. It is observed that the fraction of alcohol molecules held perpendicular to the surface of the protein decreases from 0.91 for methyl to 0.25 for amyl alcohol. The values of thermodynamic functions indicate that there is no chemical interaction between the adsorbent and the adsorbate.

EARLIER work on the sorption of vapours on proteins has established that the degree of cross-linking whether inter- or intra molecular plays a vital role in the sorption process¹⁻⁴. Sorption on proteins occurs on specific sites⁵. Since only polar sorbates are strongly adsorbed on such substances, this suggests that the main attractive forces of the sorbent for the sorbate are due to electrostatic attraction of permanent dipoles⁶. Keeping this view, it would be of interest to examine the sorption problem of a series of polar adsorbates of increasing chain length.

This paper summarises the results of a comparative study of the sorption of methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl, *n*-butyl and *n*-amyl alcohols on egg albumin. The role of molar volume and chain length in the sorption mechanism has been discussed. Studies of the sorption of alcohols of low molecular weights on egg albumin are also of particular interest because these do not cause as much swelling of the protein network as is produced with water, although they are similar to water in some aspects of chemical properties.

Experimental

Egg albumin used was purchased from M/s Sigma Chemicals, St Louis, Missouri (U.S.A.). The salt free, crystallised, lyophilised and freeze dried sample was over 99% pure and its purity was checked by electrophoresis on cellulose acetate paper in barbital buffer of pH 8.6 and ionic strength of 0.75 which was in agreement with manufacturer's specifications. The particle size was that of 100 mesh British standard sieve. The alcohols of Analar grade were supplied by M/s British Drug House, Bombay.

The quartz fibre spring technique described elsewhere⁷ has been employed for sorption work. The sorption apparatus was kept at 30° inside an air thermostat of the type built by Vernon⁸. An Edwards high vacuum pump which produces a pressure of 10⁻² mm was used. A cathetometer, reading correct to within 10⁻² mm, was employed for measuring the length and stretch of the spring.

Results and Discussion

Sorption process: The studies revealed that the rate of adsorption of alcohol on egg albumin was

sluggish and equilibrium was established in less than 8 hrs after the sample was exposed to the vapour. Actually the vapour were allowed to remain in contact with the adsorbent for 12 hrs each. The isotherms are plotted in Fig. 1. The amount of sorbate taken at saturation pressure of methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl, *n*-butyl and *n*-amyl alcohol are 14.9, 13.4, 12.0, 8.9 and 7.6 percent of albumin respectively

Fig. 1—Adsorption Isotherms
△—Methyl Alcohol
×—Ethyl Alcohol
▲—*n*-Propyl Alcohol
○—*n*-Butyl Alcohol
●—*n*-Amyl Alcohol

Now as far as protein structure is concerned, the basic elements of it are essentially polypeptide chains which instead are made up of any of the twenty different amino acids. The number of each and the sequence of their incorporation into the polypeptide chain determines the primary structure of the protein. The secondary structure refers to the way in which the polypeptide chain is coiled into a helix or spiral as a consequence of the links and bonds between relatively close elements of the chain. The tertiary structure describes how the coiled polypeptide chains are arranged in space, folded or packed into the protein molecule by side chain interactions which can be of several kinds; important ones being hydrogen bonds, hydrophobic bonds, electrostatic forces, dispersion forces and $\pi-\pi$ interactions. There is a concerted cooperation between different types of forces giving rise to an ordered

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structure^{9,10}. It is known that the polypeptide chains tend to fold in such a way so as to expose a maximal number of hydrophilic amino acid residues to the aqueous environment and to enclose a maximum number of hydrophobic residues. Thus one finds predominantly polar chemical groups on the surface of the protein and non-polar groups in the interior.

It is postulated¹¹ that the adsorption of alcohol initially occurs on the surface of the protein. The molecules then diffuse into the interior of the sorbent where the binding groups are the free basic and acidic groups. The initial diffusion is accompanied by a progressive swelling of the protein net work to some extent and binding to these active centres increases. The higher pressure finally leads to multimolecular adsorption of the surface.

The dipole moment values of the alcohols under study are almost the same these being 1.70, 1.69, 1.66, 1.66 and 1.62 Debye units for methyl, ethyl, *n*-propyl, *n*-butyl and *n*-amyl respectively. The molar volumes of the alcohols in the same order are 24.06, 33.81, 44.09, 91.53 and 62.51 cc respectively (at 25°). A comparison of the sorptive capacity and molar volume suggests that decrease in the extent of sorption from methyl to *n*-amyl alcohol is due to an increase in the molecular size. There is approximately 1.5% decrease in sorption for an increase of one methylenic group in the alcohol. The adsorption occurs on the freely exposed surface followed by penetration and promoted by swelling to some extent, so the energy barrier for the second process will be higher, the longer the chains. This may be due to a rapid increase in steric effects such as space requirements, shielding of lone-pairs etc. Also the low concavity of the adsorption isotherms to the pressure axis at low pressure may be due to the fact that some of the sorption sites are inaccessible because of the large molar volume of the sorbate and the physical structure of the sorbent. These observations are fully supported by the work of Puri and Malik¹² who showed that sorption of water by casein was more in comparison to methanol which instead was greater than that of ethanol. Gupta and Bhatia¹³ in their studies on the sorption of water, methanol, ethanol and carbon tetrachloride on starch also observed an inverse relationship between molar volume of sorbate and the sorption capacity of starch.

Application of the BET equation: The adsorption isotherms (Fig. 1) are of sigmoid shape, which according to the BET theory¹⁴ are classified as type II isotherms. This indicates that the sorption of alcohols by egg albumin is multimolecular in nature. The BET equation¹⁵ is applicable here.

$$\frac{p}{x(p_0 - p)} = \frac{1}{x_m \cdot c} + \frac{c - 1}{x_m^2 \cdot c} \cdot \frac{p}{p_0} \dots\dots(1)$$

where p/p_0 is the relative vapour pressure, x is the amount of sorbate in g adsorbed per 100 g of sorbent, x_m is the monolayer capacity and c is a constant related to the heat of adsorption. From the slope and intercept of each plot (Fig. 2) the value of the monolayer capacity (x_m) has been calculated for five alcohols.

From these values and the cross-sectional area (A_m) of alcohol molecule¹⁶, the specific surface area (S) of egg albumin has been evaluated from the equation¹⁵

$$S = \frac{x_m}{M} \cdot N \cdot A_m \cdot 10^{-20} \dots(2)$$

where N stands for the Avogadro number. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Fig. 2.—Application of the BET Equation
 Δ — Methyl Alcohol
 × — Ethyl Alcohol
 ▲ — *n*-Propyl Alcohol
 ○ — *n*-Butyl Alcohol
 ● — *n*-Amyl Alcohol

TABLE 1—VALUES OF MONOLAYER CAPACITY (x_m), MOLECULAR CROSS SECTION (A_m) AND SPECIFIC SURFACE (S) FOR ALCOHOL-EGG ALBUMIN SYSTEM

	x_m (g/g of adsorbent)	A_m (Å ²)	S (m ² /g)
Methyl alcohol	0.0606	21.2	241.8
Ethyl alcohol	0.0326	27.0	115.2
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	0.0176	31.4	55.91
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	0.0123	36.0	35.96
<i>n</i> -Amyl alcohol	0.0059	40.2	16.15

It is observed (Table 1) that the value of the calculated specific surface area of egg albumin decreases from methyl to *n*-amyl alcohol. Some workers^{2,17} have questioned the general application of the BET equation to the sorption of water vapour on proteins. This may by implication hold good in the case of sorption of alcohol vapour as well. But even though the absolute values may not be of importance, a comparative study of the same has led to an interesting conclusion. The reason for the higher values of surface area of the protein from adsorption of methanol and ethanol and lower values obtained from the adsorption of *n*-propanol, *n*-butanol and *n*-pentanol may be due to the fact that non-polar hydrocarbon chain in the latter blocks some

of the neighbouring adsorption sites and thus renders them inaccessible for interaction with the polar hydroxyl group of the alcohol molecules. Puri and Malik^{1,2} also obtained similar results with casein.

A part of the discrepancy in surface area values might, of course, be due to the swelling that occurs during sorption. Egg albumin comparatively swells better with methanol and ethanol than it does with the rest of the alcohols. However, it does not seem likely that the increase in surface area owing to swelling would be extensive enough to account for all these differences.

Orientation of the sorbed molecules : The aliphatic alcohols are linear in shape increasing in length from methyl to *n*-amyl alcohol. The molecules can be held on the surface of the protein either perpendicular or parallel to the surface. In these two modes of adsorption, the areas occupied by the adsorbed molecules on the sorbent surface are different on the assumption that alcohol molecule is a rectangular rod. The cross-sectional area of the rod and also the area of one of the four sides along the length of the rod are calculated. The thickness of the molecules of all the five alcohols is the same^{1,8}, namely 4.55 Å.

An attempt has been made to find out the number of molecules held perpendicular and the number held parallel to the surface. The total number of alcohol molecules (*n*) contained in the monolayer on the surface of 1 g of the adsorbent is given by

$$n = \frac{x_m \cdot N}{M} \quad \dots (3)$$

From this, the number of molecules held perpendicular to the surface (*Z*) is calculated from the following equation^{1,6} by assuming that the calculated surface of the protein is different for each alcohol :

$$Z \cdot C_a + (N - Z)S_a = S \quad \dots (4)$$

where *C_a* is the cross-sectional area and *S_a* is the side area of the linear molecules in square meters. The results are given in Table 2.

between the groups set free in this way and the hydroxyl group of the alcohol. The decrease in adsorption as one proceeds from methyl to amyl alcohol is largely connected with the inability of the larger molecules to break up the secondary network of the protein and also due to the interference of the carbon chains with each other.

Sorption is not completely oriented. The number of alcohol molecules perpendicular to the surface of egg albumin decreases sharply from methyl to *n*-amyl alcohol. Thus while 91% of the methanol molecules are perpendicular to the surface, the number drops to 25% for *n*-amyl alcohol. It is thus inferred that many alcohol molecules are held on the hydrophobic centres of the protein by Van der Waals forces^{1,2}. Our observations on the sorption of water and some straight and branched-chain aliphatic alcohols by casein which will soon be published^{1,9} strongly support these findings.

Thermodynamic functions : In order to gain an insight into the interaction of alcohols with egg albumin, the value of the net heat of adsorption in the BET equation has been calculated from the equation^{1,5}

$$c = e(E_1 - E_L)/RT \quad \dots (5)$$

where *E₁* is the heat of adsorption in the first layer and *E_L* is the latent heat of condensation. The results are recorded in Table 3. The low magnitude of the values indicates that there is no chemical interaction between the alcohol molecules and the protein. It is merely a case of physical sorption involving weak inter molecular forces. It is seen that the value of the heat of adsorption increases from 342.02 to 519.60 cal/mole with the increase in the number of carbon atoms from 1 to 4, which is then followed by a decrease to 479.80 cal/mole for the alcohol containing 5 carbon atoms. This reveals that the energy evolved is not dependent on the number of sites available for sorption. Moreover, there appears to be no precise relation between the energy liberated and length of the carbon chain of the alcohol. This probably occurs because of some other inter and intra-molecular forces which have not been taken into account.

TABLE 2—DATA FOR THE ORIENTATION STUDIES CONSIDERING ALCOHOL MOLECULES AS LINEAR

	Diameter D-Spherical	Length of the molecule	Area of side	Total number of molecules in monolayer	Number of molecules held perpendicular to the surface
	(Å)	(Å)	(Å ²)	(<i>n</i>)	(<i>Z</i>)
Methyl alcohol	4.6	4.7	21.4	114.1 × 10 ¹⁹	104.6 × 10 ¹⁹
Ethyl alcohol	5.2	6.8	30.9	42.6 × 10 ¹⁹	36.7 × 10 ¹⁹
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	5.6	8.5	38.5	17.7 × 10 ¹⁹	9.8 × 10 ¹⁹
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	6.0	10.4	47.5	9.9 × 10 ¹⁹	3.92 × 10 ¹⁹
<i>n</i> -Amyl alcohol	6.3	12.1	55.0	4.1 × 10 ¹⁹	1.02 × 10 ¹⁹

From a perusal of the data given in Table 2, it is evident that the number of molecules in the monolayer decreases as the length of the carbon chain of the alcohol increases. The adsorption phenomenon involves the breakage of the intra-molecular hydrogen bonds of the protein and the formation of new hydrogen bonds

Further in an isothermal process involving the transfer of alcohol from vapour state to the surface of the adsorbent, the free energy change, which is usually taken as a quantitative measure of the affinity of the adsorbent for the adsorbate, is given by the equation

$$\Delta G = \frac{RT}{M} \int_0^1 a \cdot \frac{dx}{x} \quad \dots (6)$$

where a is the weight of the vapour adsorbed at a relative vapour pressure x and other letters have their usual significance. In order to integrate the equation $\frac{a}{y}$ versus y has been plotted in Fig. 3. The area under the curve was multiplied by $\frac{RT}{T}$ to get the value of ΔG . The magnitudes of these values (Table 3) also rule out the possibility of any chemical interactions in the system. Free energy change for a constant pressure process is a measure of the tendency of the process to proceed spontaneously and in a series of analogous reactions, the tendency with which the processes occur are often roughly in the order of the free energy decrease. The values of free energy show a decline from 301.70 for methyl to 22.67 cal/mole for n -amyl alcohol respectively. This reveals that the spontaneity of the reaction or the affinity of the adsorbent for the adsorbate decreases as the length of the carbon chain of the alcohol increases.

Fig. 3.—Plots of a/x vs. x
 Δ —Methyl Alcohol
 \times —Ethyl Alcohol
 \blacktriangle — n -Propyl Alcohol
 \circ — n -Butyl Alcohol
 \bullet — n -Amyl Alcohol

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES AT 30°

	Heat of adsorption ($-\Delta H$, cal/mole)	Free energy change ($-\Delta G$, cal/mole)	Entropy change ($-\Delta S$, cal/deg/mole)
Methyl alcohol	342.02	301.70	0.13
Ethyl alcohol	400.40	138.40	0.86
n -Propyl alcohol	479.00	78.81	1.28
n -Butyl alcohol	519.60	48.68	1.55
n -Amyl alcohol	479.80	22.67	1.51

The values of the heat of adsorption (ΔH) and the free energy change (ΔG) have been utilised to calculate the entropy change (ΔS) which is a measure of the randomness of the system and is given by :

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad \dots (7)$$

The results are given in Table 3. Thus the values become more negative as one proceeds from methyl (0.13 eu) to n -amyl alcohol (1.51 eu). The process involving physical adsorption leads to a stage where the molecules have less degree of freedom. The alcohol molecules are thus placed, in an orderly fashion on the surface of egg albumin and the arrangement becomes better organized with the increase in the length of the carbon chain.

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